

Relevancy of Curriculum Framework for Teacher Education: A Need of the Time

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Abstract

In 1944, The American Commission on Teacher Education revealed in its reports that the contemporary social scene and the democratic way of life as points of orientation, urging that teachers become sensitive to the school's relation to social realities and ideals (as quoted in A Design for a School of Pedagogy, p.11). The Commission also recommended for the advancement of the design of teacher education programmes according to social responsibilities and development of institutions for effective implementation of teacher education programmes. Today, it is compulsory need of teachers are required to engage with the moral and social purposes of schooling, to value and sustain the intellect, to work collaboratively with other stakeholders of education, to be responsible for societal need, to be accountable for their responsibilities and to be committed to lifelong learning and reflexivity. Therefore, defined values, knowledge and skills are mandatory to impart in a curriculum for teacher education. This research article emphasises on the relevancy of the teacher education curriculum with the changing of time.

Keywords: *Curriculum, Societal needs, Teacher Education, Values, Knowledge, Skills*

Introduction :

A curriculum is considered the *heart* of any learning institution which means that schools, college or universities cannot exist without a curriculum. With its importance in formal education, curriculum has become a dynamic process due to the changes that occur in our society. Therefore, in its broadest sense, curriculum refers to the *total learning experiences of individuals not only in school, but in society as well* (Bilbao *et al.*, 2008). In most cases, the term curriculum is used to mean very different things by different users and even by the same user in different contexts (NCERT, 2006, p. 1).

In most countries the ministry of education establishes curricular standards (Burrill *et al.*, 2015). Governments influence education through funding initiatives,

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such as the Free and Compulsory Education Act 2009, Right to Education Act 2009, etc. In many countries, standards / curricular goals are set by its' historical tradition or cultural norms. For example, Namibia used the Cambridge curriculum when they became independent in 1990 and only recently has begun to develop their own standards. Brazil's curriculum standards are attributed to the history of the discipline and the comparative analysis among national documents from different historical periods with the extracts of national and international documents. Curriculums of some countries follow standards and guidelines of countries having high achievement scores on recent international exams (National Curricular Design, 2009).

Curriculum is an institutional text, the purpose of which is to simplify the everyday functioning of an institution (Pinar *et al.*, 2008, p. 661). Curriculum policy is an initial stage of curriculum development (Pinar *et al.*, 2008). However, in practice, due to constant interactions and influences, these stages do not essentially follow a strict linear sequence. More formally, curriculum policy can be defined as '*the formal body of law and regulation that pertains to what should be taught in schools*' (Elmore and Sykes, 1992 as quoted in Pinar, *et al.*, 2008, p. 666). General capabilities, which should be addressed across the curriculum, are literacy, numeracy, ICT, thinking skills, creativity, self-management, teamwork, intercultural understanding, ethical behaviour and social competence (DoE, 2011, p. 6). Because the national curriculum represents the learning entitlement of every student of the country from which he belongs (ACARA, 2009, p. 11).

NCERT (2006) defined the *curriculum framework* as *a plan that interprets educational aims vis-a-vis both individual and society, to arrive at an understanding of the kinds of learning experiences school must provide to children* (p. V of executive summary). Curriculum (what is taught) and Pedagogy (how it is taught) have always been challenging issues in the education history of India post independence. It is only natural for it to be so owing to the immense diversity in the contexts, needs, and opportunities of the country's population. The existing forms of curricula and pedagogies in the country are a result of several programs and policies that took shape over the years, particularly after independence. The following three sections briefly describe the policy context in which curriculum is designed and implemented. It begins with a brief review of literature on curriculum policy to understand how policy influences the implementation of curriculum. It is followed by a historical review of the ideologies and its impact on successive national curriculum frameworks in India. Lastly, the third section outlines some of the key documented challenges faced by educators in understanding and practicing the existing primary curriculum in the two districts (Kidwai *et al.*, 2013). First book entitled *The*

Curriculum in 1918 was published by *Franklin Bobbitt* followed by his another book *How to make Curriculum* in 1924. In 1926, the National society for the study of education in America published the year book devoted to the theme of curriculum 'The Foundation and Technique of Curriculum Construction'. This way the movement for curriculum development, from its beginning in 1890s, started becoming a vigorous educational movement across the world (NCERT, 2006, p. 3).

Objectives of Curriculum Development for Teachers :

A child starts out his journey of learning from his babyhood by feeling the nature and its things, connecting with persons and their ideas, by self-instinct and by a rudimentary type of education of his community and society. As the child learns to talk, he suggests a name first and then talks on concept of that name. Richmond (1919) believed, for a child, the most familiar and delightful presence of all is called mother; a different one, of more doubtful import is called father; there is a small place called 'bed' and a large place called 'out'; there is a state of harmony called 'good' and mysteriously discordant state called 'naughty' (p. 54). This belief brings us to make the sense by which we actually do classify contents of knowledge as curriculum. It is silliness of talking for stone in comparison with butter or cloth. It is relatively sensible, when comparing sandstone or chalk with granite or flint. Up-gradation of intelligence in accordance with the natural development of the child is the essence of elementary method. Therefore, a comprehending care (Richmond, 1919, p. 58), societal involvement (Weissglass, 1999), cultural assimilation (Barnhardt, 1981), ideal ethics (Ozar, 2001), knowledge (Scott, 2014; Sherrington, 2015), values (Ryan, 1993; Corrigan, 2014; Sulayman, 2014) and skills imparting objectives are needed to prepare an inclusive and dynamic curriculum.

Specific Functions of Curriculum Framework for Teachers :

Curriculum Framework for Teachers is like what is to be taught for each subject by the teachers. It includes large scale ideas, different concepts, essential skills and needful questions formed to accreditation and assessment teacher and learner with suitable, adequate content. Stabback (2016) prescribed that a Curriculum Framework can perform a range of specific functions, such as placing national statements of vision, socio-economic context and development, educational values and education policy in a curriculum context; setting out the vision, aims and objectives of the curriculum at the various stages of schooling, the transitions between each and links to further education, higher education, work and lifelong learning; explaining the educational philosophy underlying the curriculum and the approaches to teaching, learning and assessment that are intrinsic to that philosophy; prescribing requirements

for curriculum implementation, monitoring and evaluation, including the provision of clear advice (i) to teachers about appropriate pedagogy and assessment methodologies; (ii) to policy makers across the education system about the requirements of the curriculum and how they can contribute to the realization of the curriculum vision; (iii) providing guidelines to teacher educators and, if appropriate, textbook writers; (iv) outlining the curriculum structure, its subjects or Learning Areas and the rationale for the inclusion of each in the curriculum; (v) if appropriate, allocating time to various subjects and Learning Areas in each grade or stage. Depending on how well developed teaching and teachers are in any particular country, a curriculum framework and guidance need to have more or less prescription and countries need to know when they can move to less prescription to free up teachers to make local decisions.

Principles of Teacher Education Curriculum Development :

In 1950s, Ralph Tyler raised four basic questions in his book '*Basic Principles of Curriculum and Instruction*' which should be compulsorily followed in developing any curriculum and plan of instructions. These four questions are (i) what educational purposes should the school seek to attain; (ii) what educational learning experiences can be provided that are likely to attain these purposes; (iii) how can these educational experiences be effectively organized; and, (iv) how can we determine whether these purposes are being attained?

Tyler believed that the structure of the school curriculum also had to be responsive to three central factors that represent the main elements of an educative experience (a) the nature of the learner (developmental factors, learner's interests and needs, life experiences of learner, etc.); (b) the values and aims of society (democratising principles, ideal values, traditional ethics and attitudes); (c) the knowledge of subject matter (what is believed to be worthy and usable knowledge).

In the answering of Ralph Tyler's these four questions, following principles for developing a new curriculum framework arises.

1. Principle of needs - A curriculum development depends on needs of learner, teacher and finally of whole society. If we know the needs of these then we can think about that what kind of education would help to fulfill the needs of all of them.
2. Principle of action - We know that there is no chance of action without response. So to take from teacher, learner and society firstly we must give inputs then we can get outputs.

3. Principle of new research - A learner, teacher and society everyone is as researcher either in direct or indirect way. If a learner, teacher or society thinks; How to learn? How to teach? How to grow? These are the quality of a researcher. Researcher means that has curiosity.
4. Principle of innovations - Every new thing creates curiosity in the mind of every child. But we should never forget that we have also a child inside us. Because every person wants to know everything of the universe like newly born. There for everything which is new for us is as innovation.
5. Principle of value - Every society has itself culture, rules and regulations. These are the values of society. Every society wants to save their values by the preservation in mind of their followers. So education is the safety weapon and sprinkler of values of society. It helps to decide teacher and techniques to frame the knowledge of society.
6. Principle of transmission of information - We know that an important part of knowledge to which we remained untouched because either there was no any material developed to store data or no any suitable person found. In current scenario it is necessary to transfer the knowledge / information.
7. Principle of Child-Centered Curriculum - Those who advocate child-centered curriculum say that the child is the foundation to decide type of knowledge and the curriculum. Although the developing child and their environment is influenced by the society, needs of society and it's paramount. Francis Parker stated that many decades ago, "The centre of all movement in education is the child" (as quoted in Folsom & VanTassel-Baska, 2009, p. 14). Throughout the last three decades, three main child-centered curriculum movements have aroused to affect education and open education.

Need of the Curriculum Framework for Teachers :

Over time, many countries have changed from local standards to national standards. For example, Brazil found that the lack of national standards contributed to unequal opportunity for education (Cho, 2015, p. 6). The commitment towards achieving equality through education has consistently and unequivocally been voiced through the policy documents of independent India, including the reports of the two Commissions related to school education and the National Policy on Education 1986 with its review in 1992 (NCERT, 2006, p. 3). The analysis of various policy documents clearly indicates that achieving equality through education has been consistently and unequivocally voiced, over the years. However, the challenge of translating the vision of equality into a curriculum framework has remained unanswered. The basic problem that emerges has been conceptualising flexibility or

diversity which is closely linked to the systems inherent limitation and inability to define the role of the *curriculum* and its transaction. Related to this are the associated problems in defining *syllabus*, *standards* and going beyond the *core* curriculum. This reluctance of the system to allow for true plurality and flexibility in the curriculum, as well as the restricted meaning of the term curriculum itself is most clearly evident in the report *Learning without Burden* (Yashpal Committee, 1993).

The subsequent Education Commission (1964-66) continued to highlight the poor quality of school education and commented on the low quality of textbooks, owing to the lack of research related to their preparation and production, and the lack of interest of top ranking scholars in this area. It called for the definition of *national standards* and recommended centralised textbook production to conform to those, starting at the national level and also supporting establishment of bodies at the State level. In hindsight, we can see that the problematic role of the textbook continuing from the colonial education system, which has assumed a sacrosanct position in the school and the classroom, marginalising the role of the curriculum and the syllabus, was further strengthened from the then expectation that the nationally produced textbook would far more precisely indicate the national standards (Educational Commission Report, 1971).

Trivialisation of the Curriculum :

Curriculum and therefore learning and participating in school can be trivialized. Such trivialisation can lead to rendering schooling irrelevant and meaningless for many students. A summary of trivialisation appears below (Wood, 1990). Wiggins and McTighe (2007) expressed their frustration for uncomfortable relationship between teachers and curriculum in *Schooling by design: mission, action and achievement* that "Over the years, we have observed countless examples of teachers who, though industrious and well meaning, act in ways that suggest that they misunderstand their jobs. It may seem odd or even outrageous to say that many teachers misconceive their obligations. But we believe this is the case. Nor do we think this is surprising or an aspersion on the character or insight of teachers. We believe that teachers, in good faith, act on an inaccurate understanding of the role of teacher because they imitate what they experienced, and their supervisors rarely make clear that the job is to cause understanding, not merely to march through the curriculum and hope that some content will stick" (p. 128).

Encouragements for the Quality Curriculum :

Knowledge and education are considered as the major factors contributing to the sustainable development, economic growth and reduction of poverty. It is the

curriculum that is inversely viewed as the foundation for educational reforms aimed at the achievement of high-quality learning outcomes. The curriculum represents consciously, systematic selection of knowledge, skills and values to shapes the way of learning, teaching and assessment are organised by addressing questions such as what and, why, when and how students should learn. A curriculum lies at the crossroads of these four key aspects of Sustainable Developmental Goal that education should (i) be inclusive and equitable, (ii) characterized by quality learning, (iii) promoting lifelong learning and (iv) relevant to holistic development. Curriculum provides the bridge between education and development and it is the competencies associated with lifelong learning and aligned with development needs, in the broadest, holistic sense of the term, that span that bridge (Stab back, 2016, p. 4). In broad, the curriculum is also understood and treated as a political and social agreement which reflects societies shared and common visions while taking into account of local, national and global expectations. The International Bureau of Education has such a global mandate to support the development of good quality curricula in the Member States of UNESCO (Stab back, 2016, p. 6).

Suggestive Role of a Teacher in Framework :

According to *Ornstein (1982)* subject centered curriculum cannot be sufficient for the complete learning and development of a learner but a child centered curriculum can help to impart essential key knowledge through a teacher. Therefore, a teacher should be trained thus type that he encourages learner like Rousseau and John Dewey whose single purpose was to pierce ideas into a child's brain. So that a teacher can be able to play a role of (i) problem solver for learner and society; (ii) communicator between learner and society; (iii) developer of society through development of learner; (iv) actor to play their role honestly; (v) savior of culture of society; (vi) constructor of values of society; (vii) philosopher to generate power to enrich the learners with logic; (viii) psychologist to all round development of learner and to know the need of learner and society; (ix) sociologist to know about the society and interaction with its environment; (x) creative thinker to help generate convergent and divergent thinking in the mind of learner; (xi) counselor to guide the learner to make decision properly; (xii) transformer to transform the knowledge; (xiii) evaluator or Examiner to evaluate the knowledge of learner; and, (xiv) trainer of skills to train the hand through training of mind.

National Curriculum Framework for Teacher Education (NCFTE) 2009

Some time for teacher we hear some words that you are the future maker, you are ideal. An old and general thinking is that a teacher wants to see movie or film is a

bad teacher. But role of a teacher in movie/film liked by us. An example from me that in year 2007 a movie released namely "*Taare Zameen par*" gives a massage to the teachers of the world. In the movie how a teacher understands the problems of child and helps him by knowing his interest in painting. On the other side stick lover teacher were there to afraid the children. There was a characteristic to interact with children. We need not a teacher only like a mother or like a father. A teacher who has quality of father and mother both will be a good teacher. A curriculum for teacher should be versatile and globally valid.

NCFTE-2009 is envisaged to act as a channel to change the shape of teacher education so that the teacher education institutions grow to be active centers not only of make inquiries but also of training intended for improvement of educational technique and curriculum. It is an issue of certainty that if teacher education institutions could be structured on accordance to rules and become active centers of progressive educational actions, the complete task of educational reform would be seriously facilitated. This framework shows implementation strategies as follows -

1. NCFTE-2009 advocates the correction at any stage in this framework with great suggestions that are given by the NCERT, NGOs, SCERTs, DIETs, CIE, RIEs, Universities and other personalities.
2. The NCTE will organize groups of scholars to implement the NCFTE-2009, its processing and provisions.
3. The NCFTE-2009 has suggested the requirement for exercise to prepare the teachers for the co-curricular activities for health and environmental education and effectively serve the services related to these particular areas.
4. This NCFTE-2009 gives suggestion to organize training programme for professional development of teacher all-round the country.
5. In NCFTE-2009 steps are updated to promote and proved openness to the special and talented in teacher education programme.

It suggests that evaluation of In-service and Pre-service teacher must be done on the basis of CCE (Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation) during training and teaching session.

Conclusion :

The role of the teacher in classrooms is changing due to the relentless pressure for performing well. The demands of various mandated curriculum and the ubiquitous concerns about quality teaching are making teachers unconfident in their own practiced abilities. There is narrow space left for them to make their own decisions

and act on their own ideas and knowledge as educators. Therefore, it is need of time to start reclaiming the notion of teacher as curriculum worker that is someone, who can translate and transform their professional knowledge into appropriate conditions for learning for their particular students in their particular places. The development in learners of broadly defined strength and abilities, such as creative and divergent thinking depends on the integration of three main learning aspects as values, knowledge and skills. Therefore, defined *values* (attitude, moral behaviour, motivation, will and wishes, and commitment, etc.), *knowledge* (mainly knowledge refers to a body of facts and principles accumulated by mankind in the course of time) (Clarke, 1992) and *Skills* (the ability to use one's knowledge effectively and readily in execution or performance are mandatory to impart in a curriculum) need to be inculcated in the crop of new generation or future of the country.

References :

- ACARA (2009). *National Report on Schooling in Australia 2009* (pp. 1-125, Rep.). Sydney: Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority.
- Barnhardt, R. (1981). *Culture, Community and the Curriculum*. Article, Center for Cross Cultural Studies, University of Alaska Fairbanks, Fairbanks. Retrieved on 2017, August 19 from <http://www.ankn.uaf.edu/Curriculum/Articles/RayBarnhardt/CCC.html>
- Bilbao, P. P.; Lucido, P. I.; Iringan, T. C. and Javier, R. B. (2008). Curriculum development. Philippines: Lorimar Publishing, Inc.
- Bourdieu, P. (1985). Principles for reflecting on the curriculum. *The Curriculum Journal*, 1(3), pp. 307-314.
- Buckingham, D. (2013). *Media education: Literacy, learning and contemporary culture*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons.
- Burrill, G., Lappan, G., & Gonulates, F. (2015). Curriculum and the Role of Research. In S. J. Cho (Ed.), *The Proceedings of the 12th International Congress* (pp. 247-263). East Lansing: Michigan State University.
- Cho, S. J. (2015). *The Proceedings of the 12th International Congress on Mathematical Education Intellectual and attitudinal challenges*. Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Clarke, R. (1992, September 13). Knowledge. Retrieved August 16, 2017, from <http://www.rogerclarke.com/SOS/Know.html>
-

- Corrigan, D. (2014). Curriculum and Values. In *Encyclopedia of Science Education* (pp. 1-4). Springer Netherlands.
- Dewey, J. (1934). *Experience and Education*. New York, NY: Free Press.
- DoE, (2011). *Review of the National Curriculum in England* (pp. 1-128, Publication No. Research Report DfE-RR178a). The Department of Education.
- Educational Commission Report (1971), *Education and National Development: Report of the Education Commission 1964-66*, NCERT: New Delhi.
- Folsom, C. & VanTassel-Baska, J. (2009). *Teaching for Intellectual and Emotional Learning (TIEL): A Model for Creating Powerful Curriculum*. Lanham, Maryland: Rowman and Littlefield Education. p. 14.
- Freire, P. (1970). *Pedagogy of the Oppressed*. London: Continuum International Publishing Group.
- Kidwai, H., Burnette, D., Rao, S., Nath, S., & Bajaj, M. (2013). *The Policy and Practice of Public Primary Curriculum in India*. (Columbia Global Centers-South Asia, Mumbai): Columbia University. p. 15.
- National Curricular Design, (2009). Lima, Peru: Ministry of Education.
- NCERT, (2006). *Curriculum, Syllabus and Textbooks: Position Paper of National Focus Group (2.3)*. NCERT: New Delhi.
- NCERT, (2006). *Curriculum, Syllabus and Textbooks: Position Paper of National Focus Group (2.3)*. NCERT: New Delhi. p. V (of Executive Summary).
- Ornstein, A. C. (1982, February). Curriculum Contrasts: A Historical Overview. *Phi Delta Kappan*, 404-408.
- Ozar, D. T. (2001). Learning Outcomes for Ethics Across the Curriculum Programs. *Teaching Ethics*, 2(1), 1-27. doi:10.5840/tej2001211
- Pinar, W., Reynolds, W., Slattery, P. and Taubman, P. (2008). *Understanding Curriculum*. New York: Peter Lang. p. 661-666.
- Richmond, K. (1919). *The Curriculum*. London: Constable & Company Limited.
- Ryan, K. (1993). Mining the Values in the Curriculum. *Educational Leadership*, 51(3), 16-18.
- Scott, D. (2014) Knowledge and the curriculum, *The Curriculum Journal*, 25:1, 14-28, DOI: 10.1080/09585176.2013.876367
-

- Sherrington, T. (2015). An Inclusive Curriculum for All: Knowledge and the National Baccalaureate. In J. Simons & N. Porter, *Knowledge and the Curriculum* (pp. 51-54). London: Policy Exchange.
- Skill, (2017). Retrieved August 16, 2017, from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/skill>
- Stabback, P. (2016). *What Makes a Quality Curriculum?* (Vol. 2, pp. 1-41, Rep. No. IBE/2016/WP/CD/02). International Bureau of Education (UNESCO).
- Sulayman, H. I. (2014). Values-Based Curriculum Model: A Practical Application of Integrated 'Maqasid Al-Sharia' for Wholeness Development of Abstract Mankind [Research Article]. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 123, 477-484.
- Tyler, R. W. (1949). *Basic principles of curriculum and instruction*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- UNESCO, (1998). "World Declaration on Higher Education for the Twenty First Century: Vision and Action". Retrieved on 21 Sept. 2015. http://www.unesco.org/education/educprog/wche/declaration_eng.htm#world%20declaration
- UNESCO, (2017). The curriculum. Retrieved on 2017, August 14 from http://www.unesco.org/education/tlsf/mods/theme_a/popups/mod05t01s01.html
- Weissglass, J. (1999, April 21). Curriculum and Society. *Education Week e-newsletter*, 18, 45-47.
- Wiggins, G. & McTighe, J. (2007). *Schooling by design: mission, action and achievement*. Heatherton, Vic: Hawker Brownlow Education. p. 128.
- Wood, G. H. (1990). Teachers as Curriculum Workers. In J. T. Sears and J. D. Marshall, *Teaching and thinking about curriculum: Critical inquiries* (pp. 97-109). New York: Teachers College Press.
- Yarbrough E. V., Bruce W. C. & Hubright R. L. (Ed.) (1974). *Readings in curriculum and supervision*. New York: Irvington Publishers. p. 226.
- Yashpal Committee Report (1993). *Learning without Burden: Report of the National Advisory Committee, Ministry of Human Resource Development*. New Delhi, pp. 1-26.
